
GUT2BEHAVE - Metabolic profiling of the gut-brain axis as a new stratification process to improve behavioural disorders: proof of concept in alcohol dependence

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline.be

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Project abstract:

Alcohol dependence affects 5 to 10% of the population in industrialized countries and is a leading cause of premature death. Patients with alcohol use disorder (AUD) are prone to develop emotional and cognitive symptoms that increase the risk of relapse, and the current treatments have limited efficacy for most patients. Our previous data show that AUD patients display alterations of gut microbiota composition and function and emphasize the possible causal role of altered gut microbiota in emotional disturbances and brain inflammation. The interest of the project is to propose biomarkers involved in gut-brain axis to control emotional and cognitive functions to better stratify patients and to design innovative treatment of AUD. By taking advantage of biological samples in existing cohorts of AUD patients (feces, blood, post-mortem brain), we will search for relevant metabolites (untargeted metabolomics) reflecting brain, behavioural and metabolic alterations related to gut microbiota. The relevance of the selected biomarkers in other pathophysiological contexts and the influence of confounding factors will be evaluated in existing cohorts of obese and elderly patients. Original preclinical and in vitro studies will dissect the mechanisms through which the selected metabolite(s) influence central nervous system function and behaviour. Finally, we will examine whether a nutritional strategy targeting the gut microbiota (intervention study in AUD and obese patients treated with inulin-prebiotics versus placebo) is able to modulate these metabolites and if this modulation is related to the improvement of mood and cognitive disturbances. The GUT2BEHAVE project innovates in the scientific rationale and health care for psychiatric

diseases that require personalized approach.

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Version information

Version number

DMP GUT2BEHAVE cohorts -v2.0

Description

update of the initial DMP (submitted in month 8) for the first periodic evaluation of the project.

Date of first version

15/12/2020

Date of last update

26/09/2022

1. Data summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of the data collection/generation in the GUT2BEHAVE project is to obtain quantitative data to reach GUT2BEHAVE's objectives, namely identification of biomarkers linking gut microbiota to psychological alterations in patients with Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD). Serum, brain and fecal untargeted metabolomics will be correlated with psychological symptoms and gut microbiota (WP1). The relevance of these biomarkers for patients presenting mood and cognitive disturbances in other contexts (elderly and obese patients) will be evaluated (WP2).

The data generation and collection will comply with the national and EU ethics and legal requirements.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

1. DATA TYPE 1: Data generated from untargeted metabolomics analyses in different sample types:
 - o blood and the fecal matter of AUD patients (GUT2BRAIN cohort) to identify potential neuroactive metabolite(s) associated with mood disorders
 - o blood of AUD patients (AlcoholBis cohort) to identify potential neuroactive metabolite(s) associated with cognition
 - o post-mortem brain and cerebrospinal fluid of AUD patients (TSDS cohort) to evaluate the ability of the selected metabolite(s) to cross the blood-brain barrier
 - o blood and fecal matter of obese patients (FOOD4GUT cohort) to extend the neuroactive properties of selected metabolite(s) to other clinical populations
 - o blood of selected aged subjects with or without nutritional intervention (Nutrimemo cohorts) to extend the neuroactive properties of selected metabolite(s) to other clinical populations and link it to cognitive and mental health
- LC-MS data acquisition for non-targeted metabolic profiling: liquid chromatography utilizing reversed phase and hydrophilic interaction chromatographic separation techniques – quadrupole-time-of-flight-mass spectrometry (Bruker Elute UHPLC; Impact II QTOF) with positive and negative ionization modes allowing characterization of compounds from very wide range of chemical properties. Raw data extraction and alignment will be carried out using MSDial and MSFinder (http://prime.psc.riken.jp/Metabolomics_Software/MS-DIAL/) followed by data pre-processing involving quality assurance.

Identification of the metabolite(s) using retention time and MS/MS fragmentation data will be computer-assisted using state-of-the-art prediction tools and compared against online spectral libraries and in-house compound libraries (ca 1000 compounds) and pure compounds acquired within this project. Data output: Raw data in measured LC-MS files and combined data matrix in Excel files.

- The gut production of short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) will be measured from the fecal samples by solid phase microextraction coupled to gas chromatography and mass spectrometry⁵¹ (SPME-GC-MS; Thermo Trace 1310 – TSQ 8000 Evo, Thermo Scientific; SPME: Supelco fused silica capillary column SPB-624, (30 m x 0.25 mm x 1.4 µm). The system is operated using Xcalibur 4.0 and compounds will be quantified by comparing to external standards. Data output: Raw data in measured GC-MS files and combined data matrix in Excel files.
1. DATA TYPE 2: Data related to gut microbiota composition obtained from fecal matter (Gut2brain, FOOD4GUT, TSDS cohorts) to identify the origin of neuroactive metabolite(s): data generated with the analysis of Illumina sequencing: fastq and excel files

 1. DATA TYPE 3: Data related to psychological outcomes associated with mood and sociability (depression, anxiety, alcohol craving, social impairments) obtained from Gut2brain cohort to identify potential neuroactive metabolite(s) associated with mood disorders: Excel files

 1. DATA TYPE 4: Data related to cognitive functions (including brain imagery and connectivity using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI)) obtained from Alcoholbis, Nutrimemo cohorts to identify potential neuroactive metabolite(s) associated with cognition: Excel files

 1. DATA TYPE 5: Data related to inflammation, nutrition, liver functions, lipid profile, glucose homeostasis obtained from Gut2brain, FOOD4GUT, NUTRIMEMO cohorts to identify the potential confounding factors influencing the levels of the neuroactive blood metabolite(s) (nutritional status, inflammatory status, body mass index, metabolic disturbances): Excel files

 1. DATA TYPE 6: Data related to neuro-psychological parameters, inflammation, nutrition, lipid profile, metabolism from Nutrimemo cohort: Excel files (Projects)

 1. DATA TYPE 7: Data generated with PCR analysis of microbiota: Excel files

Will you re-use any existing data and, if so, how?

Yes, several existing data were obtained before the start of the GUT2BEHAVE project and will reuse for correlation analyses:

- Data generated from untargeted metabolomics analysis in the blood of obese patients (FOOD4GUT cohort) issued from the METABIOTIX project (PDR T.0068.19 financed by Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique (FRS)-FNRS). The study was approved by the Ethics Committee "Comité d'éthique Hospitalo-facultaire de Saint-Luc" (Cliniques Saint-Luc, Brussels, Belgium) with approval Code: 2014/26SEP/488 (first approval Date: 22/02/2016; approved amendment for data/material re-use in the context GUT2BEHAVE project: 18/03/2019). The trial protocol was published on protocols.io (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.baidica6). The trial was registered in the clinicaltrials.gov registry (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT03852069).
- Data generated from untargeted metabolomics analysis of brain and CSF samples from the TSDS cohort. The ethical approval is from Valvira (Dnro 564/05.01.00.06/2010).
- Data related to psychological outcomes associated with mood and sociability (depression, anxiety, alcohol craving, social impairments) obtained from Gut2brain cohort: issued from the ARC convention (ARC18-23/092). The trial protocol was published on protocols.io (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bvs2n6ge). The study was approved by the Ethics Committee "Comité d'éthique Hospitalo-facultaire de Saint-Luc" (Cliniques Saint-Luc, Brussels, Belgium (N°2017/04JUL/354; date of approved amendment for data/material re-use in the context of GUT2BEHAVE project: 06/03/2020). The trial was registered in the clinicaltrials.gov registry (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT03803709).
- Data related to cognitive functions (including brain imagery and connectivity using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI)) obtained from Alcoholbis: issued from the ARC convention. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee "Comité d'éthique Hospitalo-facultaire de Saint-Luc" (Cliniques Saint-Luc, Brussels, Belgium (N°2014/31DEC/614 for AUD patients and 2014/14AOU/438 for control subjects; date of approved amendment for data/material re-use in the context of GUT2BEHAVE project: 06/03/2020).
- Data related to cognitive functions obtained from Nutrimemo cohort: issued from Nutrimemo project (CPP 2012/61 enregistrement 2012-A01077-36)
- Data related to gut microbiota composition obtained from fecal matter (Gut2brain, FOOD4GUT, TSDS): issued from the ARC, FOOD4GUT and TSDS projects, respectively.
- Data related to inflammation, nutrition, liver functions, lipid profile, glucose homeostasis obtained from Gut2brain, FOOD4GUT, Nutrimemo cohorts: issued from the ARC, FOOD4GUT and Nutrimemo projects, respectively.

What is the origin of the data?

- FOOD4GUT cohort:
 - PI Nathalie Delzenne (UCLouvain): data related to metabolomic analysis of the serum performed in the context of METABIOTIX project financed by Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique (FRS-FNRS) (PDR T.0068.19.)
- - PI Nathalie Delzenne (UCLouvain): data related to microbiota analysis of the fecal matter performed in the context of FIBERTAG project financed by SPW-EER (convention 1610365, ERA-HDHL cofunded call BioNH 2016; convention 1318148, programme d'excellence,)
 - PI Nathalie Delzenne and Jean-Paul Thissen (UCLouvain): data related to inflammation, nutrition, liver functions, lipid profile, glucose homeostasis obtained in the context of FOOD4GUT project financed by SPW-EER (convention 1318148, programme d'excellence,)
- GUT2BRAIN cohort: PI Nathalie Delzenne, Philippe de Timary and Peter Starkel (UCLouvain): data related to microbiota analysis of the fecal matter and data related to inflammation, nutrition, liver functions, lipid profile, glucose homeostasis in the context of a project financed by UCLouvain (Action de Recherche Concertée ARC18-23/092)
- AlcoholBis cohort (and control subjects): PI Philippe de Timary and Peter Starkel (UCLouvain)
- TSDS cohort: PI Kati Hanhineva (University of Turku, metabolomics data) Eloise Mikkonen, Pekka Karhunen (University of Tampere, original cohort sample collection). The ethical approval is from Valvira (Dnro 564/05.01.00.06/2010).
- Nutrimemo cohort: PI Project Véronique Pallet: data related to cognitive evaluation of subjects, metabolic and molecular analysis of the serum and the blood cells; inflammation, nutrition, lipid profile, obtained in the context of a project financed by the Conseil Régional d'Aquitaine (FUI NUTRIMÉMO N°F1112024B)

All the ethical issues have been addressed by focusing on the re-use of data (review of the informed consents, the consortium agreement) of the existing cohorts. Some amendments were required and obtained for data/material re-use in the context of GUT2BEHAVE project (see in the previous section). No further amendment with national relevant authorities is required. In addition, all Material Transfer Agreements (MTA) between GUT2BEHAVE partners have been established when required:

- MTA between UCLouvain & UTU for AlcoholBis samples
- MTA between UCLouvain & UTU for Gut2brain samples
- MTA between UCLouvain & UTU for FOOD4GUT samples
- MTA between NutriNeuro & UTU for NUTRIMÉMO samples

What is the expected size of the data (if known)?

approximately 35 GB for each cohort (175 GB in total)

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

- All the partners of the GUT2BEHAVE consortium (PIs and researchers)
- Other researchers working in the field of mental health
- MD in charge of patients with mental health

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?

Yes

We will provide metadata for each dataset related to metabolomic analyses (DATA-TYPE 1) and to gut microbiota analyses (DATA TYPE 2). Metadata format will follow the metadata standards requested by the data repository:

- DATA-TYPE 1: all metabolomics data will be deposited to MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>) in case of publication acceptance, except for the TSDS cohort, where the ethical approval does not allow for deposition to data repositories.
- DATA TYPE 2: the raw sequencing data about gut microbiota composition are deposited into the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) of NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>) under BioProject for FOOD4GUT, GUT2BRAIN cohorts. For TSDS cohort, the raw sequencing data about gut microbiota composition is available request from the researchers (the original ethical approval does not allow for deposition to data repositories).

Other datasets related to DATA-TYPE 3,4,5,6,7 can be deposited on a case-by-case basis in the European Commission open access repository Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> only after publication acceptance of results. This repository allows for Digital Object Identifier (DOI) assignment to datasets and other types of research outputs, and also discoverability by human and machine-readable metadata. The coordinator of the GUT2BEHAVE project (Nathalie Delzenne) will make sure that all Principal Investigators and researchers involved in the data collection/generation will have to officially agree on the dataset content and authorship intended to be deposited (within full compliance with EU GDPR n°2016/679 and the requisites imposed by National laws).

Are the data produced and/or used in the project identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism?

DATA TYPE 1: a Study Identifier will be attributed to the metabolomics data that will be deposited to MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>)

DATA TYPE 2: A SRA deposit number was attributed to the raw sequencing dataset generated with the 16S rRNA gene sequencing that are available on:

- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA669275/> for FOOD4GUT cohort
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA745947/> for GUT2BRAIN cohort

DATA-TYPE 3,4,5,6,7: A Digital object identifier (DOI) will be created in case of deposit of datasets in Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>)

What naming conventions do you follow?

name of the project (G2BH)_Name of the cohort_type of analysis_abbreviation of the PI or researcher handling the data _date of the new version. The date format used follows ISO 8601
Example: G2BH_FOOD4GUT_μbiota_AN_20201116

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Each dataset will be deposited with the appropriate keywords in order to increase data discovery.

What is your approach for clear versioning?

abbreviation of the PI or researcher handling the data-date of the new version" in the name of the files will be used to manage the different versions

What metadata will be created?

A set of metadata is requested for each dataset at the moment of data publication in data repository. Metadata will be provided in the format requested by the data repository:

- Metadata from metabolomic analyses (DATA TYPE 1) on MetaboLights
- Metadata from illumina sequencing (DATA TYPE 2) on BioProject database
- Metadata for other datasets related to DATA-TYPE 3,4,5,6,7 on Zenodo

Metadata will include a collection of information to describe the document, namely the title, authors, description, publication date, file format, keywords, access rights, license, DOI, related identifiers, grant reference.

2.2. FAIR data: Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If some data is kept closed provide a rationale for doing so.

The data produced and/or used in the GUT2BEHAVE project will be revised and approved by all consortium partners before making it openly available. The consortium may decide that some data should not be made openly available before IP rights protection or access is clarified.

Only data from illumina sequencing (DATA TYPE 2) will be made openly available as the default and will be deposited on SRA

database.

Data from metabolomic analysis DATA TYPE 1 will be open after an embargo period awaiting the acceptance of manuscripts, including the one from the initial projects from where the cohort blood samples and health and biological measurements are coming from.

Other data (DATA TYPE 3,4,5,6,7) will be either open without restriction, either open after an embargo period or available with restricted access (ex: upon request which condition of access after acceptance of their written request by the projects PIs) on a case-by-case basis.

How will the data be made accessible?

DATA TYPE 1: a Study Identifier will be attributed to the metabolomics data that will be deposited to MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>)

DATA TYPE 2: A SRA deposit number was attributed to the raw sequencing dataset generated with the 16S rRNA gene sequencing that are available on:

- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA669275/> for FOOD4GUT cohort
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA745947/> for GUT2BRAIN cohort

DATA-TYPE 3,4,5,6,7: A Digital object identifier (DOI) will be created in case of deposit of datasets on <https://zenodo.org/>

Data shared among the GUT2BEHAVE consortium partners is made accessible through a secured platform (OneDrive), available only for project members (user access).

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

- http://prime.psc.riken.jp/Metabolomics_Software/MS-DIAL/
- excel

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited? Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

All processed data produced during the project will be available to the consortium through the dedicated cloud secure platform (OneDrive).

Data related with the project that is agreed to be openly available will be deposited in the current openly available repositories/databases: Zenodo, MetaboLights, BioProject database. No restrictions for SRA database. The other closed data could be provided upon request after the acceptance of manuscript only or published as open access after an embargo period.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Restriction on use of the data before their publication was defined in the Consortium Agreement of the GUT2BEHAVE project and taking into account of all Data Transfer Agreements that will be established for the different cohorts. Access to the data within the consortium will be managed through the secure platform OneDrive with a limited user access.

Only open data will be made available in MetaboLights, BioProject, and Zenodo platforms. Some restrictions to re-use will be applied on a case-by-case basis.

2.3. FAIR data: Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable? What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

By default, data produced in the GUT2BEHAVE project will be interoperable by the project members. This will be achieved by always using open or globally used data formats for data exchange. The use of open software is recommended, although for certain tasks licensed software may be used when needed. The final data will always be available in open format. Metadata from illumina sequencing and Metabolomics data are interoperable. Zenodo will assure also interoperability:

- MetaboLights is the first general purpose, open access repository for metabolomics studies, their raw experimental data and

associated metadata, maintained by one of the major open access data providers in molecular biology. MetaboLights consists of two distinct layers: 1) a repository, enabling the metabolomics community to share findings, data and protocols for any form of metabolomics study; 2) a reference layer of curated knowledge about metabolite structures and their reference spectra, as well as their biological roles, locations, concentrations, and raw data from metabolic experiments. MetaboLights is the recommended Metabolomics repository for a number of leading journals (Metabolites, PlosBiology, Metabolomics,...). The effectiveness of metabolomic profiling methods depends on the availability of public open data across a broad range of experimental methods and conditions. The MetaboLights repository seeks to fulfil this requirement. MetaboLights is specifically designed to build on prior art and to extensively collaborate with the existing databases, ensuring that data are exchanged and that assimilation efforts target gaps in the knowledge available world

- The BioProject database provides an organizational framework to access information about research projects with links to data that have been or will be deposited into archival databases maintained at members of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Consortium (INSDC, which comprises the DNA DataBank of Japan (DDBJ), the European Nucleotide Archive at European Molecular Biology Laboratory (ENA), and GenBank at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK169438/>)). Data are submitted to NCBI or other INSDC-associated databases citing the BioProject accession, thus providing navigation between the BioProject and its datasets. Consequently, the BioProject is a robust way to access data across multiple resources and multiple submission timepoints, e.g., when there are different types of data that had been submitted to multiple databases, or sequential submissions deposited over the course of a research project.
- The metadata model used in Zenodo is based on Datacite's metadata schema that is compatible with the Dublin Core (<https://dublincore.org/>) metadata standard and thus can be interpreted by OAI-PMH harvesters like those used by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>).

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

- Metadata from illumina sequencing use standard vocabularies by using BioProject database
- Metabolomics data will use standard vocabularies by using MetaboLights.
- Open data deposition in Zenodo, a domain-agnostic repository, will allow for interdisciplinary interoperability in terms of metadata and vocabularies.

2.4. FAIR data: Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

All metabolomics data that are deposited on MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>) are governed by the EMBL-EBI's [Terms of use](#) and all code is licensed under [Apache 2.0](#).

For raw sequencing data about gut microbiota composition that are deposited into the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) of NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>) under BioProject, see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/home/about/policies/>

Other datasets related to DATA-TYPE 3,4,5,6,7 will be deposited only upon request and the license will be chosen on a case-by-case basis in the European Commission open access repository Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> (only after publication acceptance of results)

When will the data be made available for re-use? If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

The data will be available after the acceptance of the first manuscript of the project

Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

The data produced and used can be re-used after the end of the project only with the agreement of the GUT2BEHAVE consortium

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

10 years

Are data quality assurance processes described?

yes.

Quality of the metabolomics data will be analyzed using quality control samples and notame analysis workflow described in detail elsewhere (Klâvus et al. 2020).

During the sequencing run, a quality score is assigned to each base call, using the Illumina's quality scoring methodology. The mean quality score for each sample was > 33.8.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these costs be covered?

No supplementary cost

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Audrey Neyrinck, the data manager

What are the costs and potential value of long term preservation?

no cost for long term preservation

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data will be stored on a secure computer located at partner's institution. Data will be safely stored on the computer of the data manager (Audrey Neyrinck) of the GUT2BEHAVE project with a backup is weekly performed by the computer support department from the UCLouvain. Data will be shared through a secure sharing platform (One Drive) with limited access user.

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

(Re)use of the data obtained from GUT2BRAIN, Alcoholbis, FOOD4GUT cohorts, in the context of the GUT2BEHAVE project were approved by the local ethical committee (Comité d'Ethique Hospitalo-Facultaire UCLouvain/Cliniques Universitaires Saint-Luc; 2017/04JUL/354, 2014/14AOU/438 and 2014/26SEP/48) and written informed consent was obtained from all subjects before inclusion in the study for all cohorts.

The ethical approval of the TSDS cohort (Valvira, Dnro 564/05.01.00.06/2010) does not allow for deposition of the data to a public data repository, and therefore the data from the TSDS cohort will be made available only via request from the researcher.

The ethical approval of the Nutrimemo cohort: CPP 2012/61 enregistrement 2012-A01077-36

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

No